

REGISTRATION OF ROAD TRAFFIC ACCIDENTS IN CAR CARRIERS

Qo'chqorov Isroiljon Tavakkal o'g'li

Andijon mashinasozlik instituti

“Transport vositalari muhandisligi” kafedrasida assistenti

[*isroilkuchkorov11@gmail.com*](mailto:isroilkuchkorov11@gmail.com)

+998-94-160-99-44

Annotation. A car carrier is a legal or private entrepreneur with the right to transport cars. Of course, accidents, minor accidents and violations of traffic rules occur with the vehicles of the car transport company.

Key words: Traffic accidents, traffic safety, road accident, injector, multi-line spraying system, fuel tank, filter, fuel pump, main fuel line, pressure regulator.

Compiling a report on accident and organizing accounting work is one of the main areas of activity of traffic safety officers. Accident statistics are the basis of a comprehensive analysis to study the cause of the accident. The correct accounting of accidents in motor vehicles and the preparation of other preliminary documents on traffic safety are the basis for giving a true assessment of the work carried out on the prevention of accidents [1, 2, 3, 4].

According to the Regulation on the procedure for accounting for traffic accidents in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan, accounting for traffic accidents 29 analysis of the causes and conditions of their origin, as well as elimination of these causes and conditions is carried out in order to [5, 6, 7, 8].

Accounting for traffic accidents is carried out by the following organizations:

- internal affairs bodies;
- legal entities whose activities are related to the use of vehicles;
- special authorized and local state authorities and other organizations that own public highways, streets of cities and other settlements;
- medical institutions keep records of persons killed or injured due to traffic accidents [9, 10, 11, 12, 13].

The government considers the problem of traffic accidents to be necessary, yet the problem is not given national priority. There are groups dealing with the problems of improving traffic safety, which are organized by international councils, and they are working without results. Some ministries are involved in solving the problem. have been done, but they look at only part of the problem responsibly and are constantly active. The mass media constantly raise the problem, but only some organizations conduct research on specific questions. The nation shows initial

interest in solving the problem of road accidents, but there is no systematic approach [14, 15, 16, 17, 18].

The government recognized that the problem would be supported by external experts, but did not give it national priority. The database of traffic accidents has been improved, specialists have improved their skills in order to have modern knowledge on road safety issues. Work is being carried out to determine the part of the road network where accidents occur most often, to analyze the causes of accidents, and to identify the risk links of road traffic participants. The National Program is being adopted, the National Road Safety Council coordinates its implementation and supports them at the regional level. Preventive work on prevention, improvement of legislation and strict measures against road users who pose a danger to other road users are being strengthened [19, 20, 21, 22, 23].

The statistical report on road traffic accidents includes only information on incidents in which there are persons killed or injured as a result of road traffic accidents. The statistical report is carried out by the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan as a departmental report. The statistical report is kept for the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regions and the city of Tashkent [24].

The database of traffic accidents has been improved, specialists have improved their skills in order to have modern knowledge on road safety issues. Work is being carried out to determine the part of the road network where accidents occur most often, to analyze the causes of accidents, and to identify the risk links of road traffic participants.

REFERENCES

1. Kuchkorov, Isroiljon ANALYSIS OF AVAILABLE PARKING SPACES IN FOREIGN COUNTRIES OF TRANSIT ROADS FOR CARGO TRANSPORTATION BY INTERNATIONAL VEHICLES // ORIENSS. 2022. №10. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/analysis-of-available-parking-spaces-in-foreign-countries-of-transit-roads-for-cargo-transportation-by-international-vehicles> (дата обращения: 01.11.2022).
2. Javlonbek Kholmiraev, Isroiljon Kuchkorov, Adhamjon Kakhkharov PROBLEMS OF CARRYING OUT AUTO TECHNICAL RESEARCH WITH THE PARTICIPATION OF TWO-WHEELED MECHANICAL VEHICLES // Central Asian Academic Journal of Scientific Research. 2022. №5. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/problems-of-carrying-out-auto-technical-research-with-the-participation-of-two-wheeled-mechanical-vehicles> (дата обращения: 01.11.2022).

3. Javlonbek Kholmiraev, Isroiljon Kuchkorov, Adhamjon Kakhkharov DETERMINING THE NEED FOR SPARE PARTS FOR SPECIAL VEHICLES OPERATING AT AIRPORTS // Central Asian Academic Journal of Scientific Research. 2022. №5. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/determining-the-need-for-spare-parts-for-specialvehicles-operating-at-airports> (дата обращения: 01.11.2022).
4. Javlonbek Kholmiraev, Isroiljon Kuchkorov, Adhamjon Kakhkharov COMPLETE ASSESSMENT OF THE QUALITY OF THE DELIVERY OF SPARE PARTS FOR THE TECHNICAL SERVICE OF THE VEHICLE FLEET // Central Asian Academic Journal of Scientific Research. 2022. №5. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/complete-assessment-of-the-quality-ofthe-delivery-of-spare-parts-for-the-technical-service-of-the-vehicle-fleet> (дата обращения: 01.11.2022).
5. Tavakkal o'g'li K. I. CHARACTERISTICS OF THE MATERIAL USED IN THE TENSILE AND COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH OF LIGHT VEHICLE DISC MATERIALS //O'ZBEKISTONDA FANLARARO INNOVATSIYALAR VA ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR JURNALI. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 20. – С. 294-296.
6. Tavakkal o'g'li Q. I. et al. YER OSTI QUVURLARIGA GRUNT BOSIMI. BIR JINSLI GRUNTDA JOYLASHGAN QUVURGA GRUNTNING O'RTACHA VERTIKAL BOSIMI //Новости образования: исследование в XXI веке. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 5. – С. 287-292.
7. Tavakkal o'g'li Q. I. et al. YER OSTI INSHOOTLARINI SEYSMIK TURG 'UNLIK, TEXNIK DIAGNOSTIKA, REKONSTRUKSIYA VA TIKLASHGA BAG 'ISHLANGAN ADABIYOTLARNI KO'RIB CHIQISH //Новости образования: исследование в XXI веке. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 5. – С. 241-245.
8. Tavakkal o'g'li K. I., Rasuljon o'g'li M. A. MODELS FOR CALCULATING THE INTERACTION OF THE SOIL WITH THE PIPELINE //Scientific Impulse. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 4. – С. 514-518.
9. Mamasoliyev B., Melikuziev A., Sotvoldiyev O. Research of Factors Affecting the Cylinder-Porshen Group Work Process //Texas Journal of Engineering and Technology. – 2022. – Т. 7. – С. 8-12.
10. Melikuziev A. et al. IMPROVING THE PERFORMANCE OF THE FUEL INJECTION SYSTEM //Development and innovations in science. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 14. – С. 10-14.
11. Ikromov N. et al. Analysis of mechanical properties of polymer bushing used in automobile industry //Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research (AJMR). – 2021. – Т. 10. – №. 3. – С. 560-563.

12. Mahammadjonov N. et al. YO 'L FREZASI KONSTRUKSIYASINING TAHLILI //Science and innovation in the education system. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 5. – C. 45-49.
13. Xalilbek o'g'li X. E. ICHKI YONUV DVIGATEL DETALLARINI QURUM BOSISHINI TEKSHIRISH //World scientific research journal. – 2023. – T. 18. – №. 1. – C. 110-115.
14. Melikuziev A. et al. IMPROVING THE PERFORMANCE OF THE FUEL INJECTION SYSTEM //Development and innovations in science. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 14. – C. 10-14.
15. Raqibbek o'g'li K. M. TUPROQQA EKISH OLDIDAN ISHLOV BERUVCHI ENERGIYA TEJAMKOR AGREGATNING TEXNOLOGIK ISHLASH SXEMASINI TANLASH //O'ZBEKISTONDA FANLARARO INNOVATSIYALAR VA ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR JURNALI. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 19. – C. 465-467.
16. o'g'li K. M. R. UNIVERSALMOLA-BORONA PARAMETRLARINI ANIQLASHTIRISH //Finland International Scientific Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities. – 2023. – T. 11. – №. 5. – C. 2285-2292.
17. Azimov, T., Raximov, A., & Tursunboyev, L. (2023). SONLAR BILAN BELGILANGAN PROEKSIYALAR. Евразийский журнал академических исследований, 3(2 Part 3), 68-72.
18. Ismailov S., Qirg'izboyev B., Bahromov A. PARKING SPACE MANAGEMENT OR TRUCKS //Models and methods in modern science. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 15. – C. 143-147.
19. Ismailov S., Qirg'izboyev B., Bahromov A. PARKING SPACE MANAGEMENT FOR TRUCKS //Models and methods in modern science. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 15. – C. 143-147.
20. Khalilov S. et al. Tojibayev Sh. – 2012.
21. Khalilov S. A. et al. Ulotrix algae of Uzbekistan. – 2012.
22. Asliddin P. et al. SILINDR-PORSHEN GURUHI ELEMENTLARINING TAVSIFI VA DVIGATELNING EFFEKTIV KO'RSATKICHLARI //Scientific Impulse. – 2023. – T. 1. – №. 11. – C. 605-611.
23. Asliddin P. et al. PORSHEN HALQASINING ISHIGA TA'SIR QILUVCHI OMILLAR //Scientific Impulse. – 2023. – T. 1. – №. 11. – C. 611-620.
24. Xusniddin o'g'li P. A. PORSHEN HALQANING UZOQ ISHLASHINI BELGILOVCHI ASOSIY KATTALIKLAR //Научный Фокус. – 2023. – T. 1. – №. 2. – C. 680-685.